

Interagency Referral Protocol on Complaints, Feedback, and Other Serious Breaches on Accountability

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Overview	1
2. Guiding principles	1
3. Minimum referral process	5
4. Managing safe and accountable referral process	6
5. Details of the two-way channels and platforms to provide feedback and for referrals	6
6. Customer Relationship Management (CRM) Software Solution	7
7. Raising Awareness to the Communities	9
8. Referring entities	9
9. Responding/Receiving entities	9
10. Minimum Referral services	11
Key Roles and Functions	11
11. Referral Reporting	13
Reporting back to the communities	14

1.) Overview

This minimum interagency referral protocol does not change or override any internal policies and procedures of the humanitarian community (*UN and other organizations*) that have established or instituted referral process on accountability to affected people (*AAP*), protection against sexual exploitation and abuse (*PSEA*) and other community engagement endeavors. Rather, this protocol supplements and contextualizes those efforts by underscoring the overall AAP complaints and feedback referral process for the Occupied Palestinian Territory (*OPT*)¹.

All responding agencies are expected to have its own minimum standards for referral (*internally and externally*), and this must relate to this protocol as part of resolving cases and issues on a shared accountability commitment.

Speed, accuracy, and overall quality of addressing and resolving feedback or complaints are highly dependent on how responsive, safe, and accessible the referral process is, how substantial the amount of collective effort exerted to resolve issues or cases in the soonest time possible, and the available resources.

2.) Guiding principles

In support to the existing PSEA Network's protocol on community-based complaints mechanism (*CBCM*)², the interagency CFM on AAP referral process comply with the following principles:

- **Respect confidentiality (*always, all the time*)**

Any joint/interagency CFM must not only prioritize the inclusive and accessible process of receiving and addressing the feedback or complaints but must also warrant a dedicated safe and secure system to keep sensitive data, provide access restrictions, and employ legal and other support in case of breach in protocol. For any referring and responding agency, it is crucial to be mindful that only disclosed information can be shared and accessed after informed consent from the person is obtained or secured.

- **Obtain informed consent (*Non-negotiable*)**

As a rule, if consent is not obtained, referral should not proceed or be accepted. It is important to explain to an individual or community member the step-by-step

¹ Minimum Standard Operating Protocols on Managing or Supporting Interagency Complaints and Feedback Mechanism.

² Protection against Sexual Exploitation and Abuse (PSEA) Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for Community-Based Complaints Mechanism (CBCM) for State of Palestine.

process and how to access it correctly and appropriately to maximize the available services and resources.

For any referring and responding agency, it is crucial to:

- a.) Always seek both oral and written permission from an individual or community member before proceeding with the recording, review, and identification of the response and further referral actions.
 - b.) Explain all possible details and available options using the preferred or trusted two-way channels. Always be mindful of the preferences of the people or community when it comes to communicating or engaging with them. Some may trust those considered analog platforms and may have difficulty adjusting to new or emerging applications. Active listening is key especially when it comes to non-verbal communication or understanding what is not being said.
 - c.) Identify and assess if an individual or community member is able to understand all the information provided to them and if they can make an informed decision based on the options provided as well. This is to underscore the importance of determining the level of capacity and maturity of each person that will undergo the referral process. The exception to this will be the level of support to be provided immediately to the welfare of children, persons with disabilities, and those experiencing any mental or psychosocial challenges.
 - d.) Always validate or confirm that an individual or community member is not forced/coerced to disclose information by other people (*family members, neighbors, service providers, and other entities*). As a rule, sharing of information must be voluntary and based on informed consent.
- **Do not raise expectations (*but consistently provide timely updates and actively reach out to affected individual as possible*)**
 - Once all services have been explained properly and that an individual or community member understood clearly, it is crucial to avoid making big promises about the outcome of the referral process. Providing update or status of the case or issue to the community member is an important part of the process but manage the level of expectations when it comes to its immediate resolution, considering its implications may undermine the overall trust to the referral process and system supporting it.
 - **Respect choices and decision-making capacities (*Non-discrimination commitment*)**

Making sense and understanding background or experience of people requires more repetitive practice and immersive experience. Understanding core humanitarian principles requires that provision of service and assistance must apply the differential gender approach appropriate for the affected people. This includes religion, tribal affiliation/ethnicity, sexual orientation, gender identity, age, disability, and distinguishing profile like level of education, language barriers, solo parent, etc.

- **Prioritize the safety and security of the individual first (*Do-No-Harm commitment*)**

The main priority for referring or responding agency is both their and affected people's safety/security in all kinds of two-way dialogue or engagement. All indicators, signs, and alert warnings that would put both sides and other people or entities on further danger must always be avoided.

Interagency AAP referral process

Awareness to the communities on AAP referral process

- a.) Humanitarian agencies (UN, INGO, Local NGOs, CSOs, Red Cross, others)
- b.) Local Media
- c.) Community groups/networks
- d.) Volunteers

3.) Minimum referral process

There are key steps to keep in mind when receiving, recording, and reviewing possible referrals and moving forward to refer those accordingly. But from the onset, referral focal points must ensure that the:

- Individual or community member is safely and securely identified and properly engaged.
- Details of the available services or resources are clearly provided and explained.
- Details of the referral process are clearly provided and explained.
- Individual or community member is properly oriented and willing to provide informed consent.
- Individual or community member voluntarily agrees with the referral process.
- Updates of the cases or issues are regularly provided or shared.

It is also important to categorize the feedback or complaints and prioritize the timeline for response actions and referrals. By adapting the interagency common timeline and categories on feedback, complaints, and other serious breaches on accountability, it is crucial to be mindful of the following:

- **Request or access for information:** 3 days upon receiving the referral. Need to indicate or identify by the concerned agency if a.) the referral is accepted or successfully closed, b.) further referral needed, c.) there are no available services, and d.) referral is not eligible.
- **Request for assistance** (*general, specific, and special*): 3 days upon receiving the referral.
- **Dissatisfaction with programs/projects' quality and delivery of services:** 5 days upon receiving the referral.
- **Dissatisfaction with staff's behavior, rude conduct, and misdemeanor** (*abusive language, harassment, and bullying*): 5 days upon receiving the referral.
- **Abuse of power and other serious breaches on accountability** (*sexual exploitation/abuse, gender-based violence, other protection related issues, fraud, and corruption*): Immediate
- **Safety, security, and other life-threatening issues:** Immediate

Immediate pertains to high or serious imminent risk to personal safety (*life threatening situation*) requiring urgent or speedy intervention within 1-48 hours.

4.) Managing safe and accountable referral process

All responding/receiving agencies must be responsive to the following critical questions:

- What is/are the main issue(s) that needs to be addressed urgently?
- When and where did this happen? Do we have additional details that may be useful to facilitate and fast track the referral process?
- Where and why should this issue be referred?
- What program or organizations should take this on?
- Who is /are the contact person(s), group(s), and other concerned agencies (*with their corresponding information details*) that can be contacted for the referral?
- How long will the process take to resolve it or if further referral to other agencies is needed?

5.) Details of the two-way channels and platforms for feedback and referrals

- **Face-To-Face/Direct Dialogue:** includes helpdesk, field staff, direct sending of mail to office/staff, community consultation, and assessment/follow-up monitoring.
- **Helpline/Hotline/SMS/IVR:** the call-for-action is to support a unified hotline and helpline, and it must be integrated to other channels.
- **Information/Community Engagement Centers and Help Desks:** managed by two or more agencies inside camps, evacuation centers, and other temporary relocation areas.
- **Safe Spaces:** specifically establish for children, women, elderlies, persons with disabilities, and other vulnerable groups inside camps, evacuation centers, and other temporary relocation areas.
- **Radio:** including listening groups organized to widen the reach of any humanitarian radio programming.
- **Complaint/Feedback/Suggestion boxes:** other agencies may still use this up inside camps, evacuation centers, and other temporary relocation areas.
- **Online/Digital platforms:** social media engagement, email, chatbot, other online applications.

6.) Customer Relationship Management (CRM) Software Solution

The CRM software solution³ will be used to support identified two-way channels or available platforms used by the communities. This is to ensure that the referral process has the broader scope for case intakes, facilitates reporting, and secures the success of the resolving issues. It will also adopt or contextualize the common interagency mechanism on the data management and responsibility, common timeline and categories on feedback and complaints, referral action, and joint analysis and reporting process underscored on the minimum CFM protocol.

As part of improving the interagency referral mechanism, the CRM will have the application programming interface (API) with the identified helplines or hotlines, social media platforms, humanitarian radio programming, and other available digital applications. This is to ensure seamless communication, efficient data handling, and streamlined support processes. These will include improve call efficiency, centralize customer interactions, and provide real-time updates, and reporting.

From the get-go, it is important that all agencies supporting helplines or hotlines, managing social media platforms, and using humanitarian radio programming will agree for an API with the CRM software solution for support integration and improve the interagency case management.

1.) Hotlines and Helplines

The CRM will integrate telephony system for call handling, user data, logging, and tracking process directly from calls, chats, or SMS, and interactive voice response (IVR).

As highlighted in the minimum protocol on interagency CFM under roles and responsibilities on two-way communication channels, agencies with dedicated hotline or helpline should have key staff or focal points managing and supporting it. **Once API is established, hotline or helpline team can use CRM caller information in real-time through digital forms.** This can include caller demographics, nature of the call, case tracking, follow-up actions, and resolutions provided. If the hotline requires anonymity for sensitive issues and other serious breaches on accountability, the CRM are customized to exclude personally identifiable information.

Part of the functionality will include the following:

³ Ona Solution System is the third-party consultant tapped by UNICEF and UNWOMEN to provide technical support on CRM for the interagency CFM.

- **Inbound calls** like sending trigger or alert to the CRM that will enable to display caller details such as ID/phone number and automatically logs in the call.
- **Outbound calls**, where operators or dedicated staff initiating calls are linked up to the CRM.
- **Call notes/tagging**, where basically the CRM has the capacity to record, and sync calls back to the CRM.
- **Case/ticket management**, crucial that all calls recorded will automatically be linked to case/tickets to highlight status or action. Each use of the hotline or helpline will be considered as a “case’ in the CRM, and this will be categorized based on the minimum protocol on interagency CFM.
- **Reporting**, all calls will be linked up to the CRM data for insights/analytics. This will include the follow-up actions or referral where cases can be assigned to specific cluster and agency for resolutions and progress should be tracked.

2.) Humanitarian Radio Programming

The API with the humanitarian radio programming will include a SMS or voice response system. In this manner, community members can send messages or responses to radio programs via direct complaints, inquiries, or actively participating in activities like perception survey, radio listening groups, and responding to public service announcements.

The info or feedback collected through SMS or IVR will automatically be sent to the CRM for aggregation and further analysis. The API will basically boost the recording, reviewing, referring, and responding process based on the emerging needs or community responses.

As highlighted in the minimum protocol on interagency CFM under roles and responsibilities on two-way communication channels, third party organization⁴ that is tapped to manage interagency humanitarian radio programming and other agencies supporting this should have key staff or focal points in place. **Once API is established, humanitarian radio programming team can use the CRM to monitor** the progress of feedback or complaints, **continuously inform** the listener, **review** trends in public sentiments, and **evaluate** the effectiveness of the radio campaigns.

This API not only increases the reach of the radio programming but also ensures that humanitarian agencies have access to actionable data to refine or recalibrate interventions. In the same way, the interface could also facilitate improving more area-

⁴ Ajyal Radio is the third-party consultant tapped by UNWOMEN to provide technical support on the interagency humanitarian radio programming.

specific messaging or target-based radio programming. This tailored program will be more responsive to actual information needs of the people and the opportunity to provide feedback.

Part of the functionality will include the following:

- **Support community interaction:** radio broadcasts steer dynamic engagement (including using or mentioning the hotline/helpline) and responses collected via SMS, IVR, or mobile apps.
- **Improve data recording:** responses or feedback provided by the community via calls, SMS, IVR and other mobile apps to the radio will be recorded properly.
- **Real time analysis and action:** dashboards analyze data (trends), insights inform future radio content or humanitarian response.
- **Closing the feedback loop:** share aggregated insights back to the community as part of the programming.

3.) Social Media Listening and Engagement

The CRM's API with any social media platforms will benefit from **data collection and dissemination** like sharing surveys, updates, trends and reports; **engagement monitoring** that includes tracking comments, likes, and shares; and **targeted notifications and feedbacking** for advocacy, campaign messaging, and other interesting activities.

As highlighted in the minimum protocol on interagency CFM under roles and responsibilities on two-way communication channels, a third-party organization⁵ that is tapped to manage social media listening and other agencies with dedicated social media platforms on AAP, should have key staff or focal points managing and supporting it. **Once API is established with the social media, the software solution can improve data recording and reporting** like survey results, consolidated trends, and issue-based updates; **data retrieval/collection** like interaction replies to comments, number of shares, and other dynamic online engagement; **user authentication**, which is more of social media login to access the CRM form or system; and **analytics synchronization**, to consolidate data rights from the social media platforms.

⁵ Social Studio is the third-party consultant tapped by UNWOMEN to provide technical support on social media listening and engagement.

Utilizing the digital CRM solution supporting the interagency CFM

7.) Raising Awareness to the Communities

Any community member has the right to know:

- How the sharing of feedback/complaints and the referral process works?
- Who are the agencies and concerned people managing or supporting it?
- How inclusive are the two-way channels?
- How responsive is the system of the interagency CFM?
- How they will be informed if there is a corresponding action to their concerns?
- Can they influence the interagency CFM to improve or recalibrate its approach?
- How do they know that all data they shared are safe and taken with utmost confidentiality?

8.) Referring entities

Sexual Exploitation/Abuse and other serious breaches on accountability referral process

10.) Key Roles and Functions

Interagency Steering Committee

It is expected that the Interagency Steering Committee will provide the overall strategic and operational guidance in dealing with any sensitive complaints that have been escalated or reported by the designated coordinators, focal points (*referral*), and other technical support staff (*operations managers/coordinator per two-way channel*).

Its primary role is to ensure agencies or organizations consistently use the minimum referral management process that systematically record, monitor, and make follow-up on referrals.

The steering committee has the task of maintaining an enabling environment that will support and facilitate the referral process among various agencies and promote accountability to affected people by:

- Reviewing regularly the responsiveness of the minimum interagency protocol for referring and responding back to feedback, complaints, and other serious breaches on accountability.
- Updating regularly the information on available services, resources, and other form of assistance across clusters, sectors, and others to maximize interagency operational support mechanism.
- Ensuring consistently that the referral and responding process inform improvement and recalibration of sector or activity specific intervention.

Coordinators and advisors from UNOCHA, UNICEF, UNWOMEN, WFP, UNWRA, and other agencies or partners (*members of the AAP Working Group, PSEA Network, and others*) will be the core members that will lead the Steering Committee. The focal points pertain to AAP and PSEA advisors or specialists, two-way channels specific lead, and other designated staff with leadership and technical know-how to support the CFM.

On AAP focal points

All identified focal points will be responsible for liaising and coordinating with internal processes of their own organization and those other agencies or entities, with other focal points as appropriate to ensure safe reception, referral, and follow-up.

Each agency or cluster should at least have an AAP focal point to facilitate referral process internally once it receives the specific feedback or complaints, and to confirm the type of services or responses needed.

On PSEA focal points

All identified PSEA focal points will be responsible for liaising and coordinating with the investigative bodies of their own organizations and other agencies or entities, with other PSEA focal points as appropriate to ensure safe reception, referral, and follow-up.

For sensitive complaints and other serious breaches on accountability, each agency should at least have a PSEA focal point that will liaise and facilitate the referral process and ensure corresponding services are provided.

Both AAP and PSEA focal points are expected to report to each designated Coordinators or Advisors for further guidance and additional support. Both AAP and PSEA coordinators or advisors are core members of the Steering Committee on the interagency CFM.

For agencies co-leading specific clusters, AAP and PSEA focal points can directly liaise and coordinate with the cluster coordinators or focal points for immediate referral and response actions.

For referring agency:

- Referral focal point/team must be aware of the existing interagency service mapping so that services and assistance are accurately identified.
- Referral focal point/team should check if the trusted/preferred CF channels used by concerned individual are functional and responsive.
- Referral focal point/team must always be prepared to assist/facilitate the initial requirements to support concerned individual such as accessing information services available, obtaining the informed consent form, completing the interagency referral form, and identifying the right or relevant service provider.
- Referral focal point/team should properly record and review the referral made. Its role is not yet done after sending the request to the receiving/responding agency, as referral status needs to be followed up, and lastly, reporting and documenting need to be completed in compliance with the agreed interagency monitoring platform.

- Referral focal point/team, in close coordination with the responding/responsible focal point/team, needs to analyze and monitor any gaps in the referral process.
- Referral focal point/team may declare close or successful the referral case once notified by the receiving/responsible agency that response actions or services have been provided.
- Referral focal point/team may declare that the referral process is not successful and may recommend further referral as deem necessary.

For receiving/responding agency:

- Referral focal point/team should be quick to acknowledge receipt of the referral and confirm acceptance within 24 hours to 48 hours as possible.
- Referral focal point/team assesses and reviews the criteria /eligibility of the issue or case referred. This usually takes time but receiving/responsible agency should be prepared of the likely response, consequence, and additional layers of re-evaluating the appropriate actions
- Referral focal point/team needs to provide feedback in the soonest time possible after the referral is accepted and services, response actions, or interventions are provided or delivered.
- Responding/responsible agency may inform the referring agency that the referral process is closed, successful, complied, or delivered.
- Referral focal point/team also needs to provide the feedback in the soonest time possible that the referral is not accepted and provide explanations or necessary details as may be required.
- Responding/referring agency may refer/forward the case to another relevant service provider and with due diligence, the agency needs to be fully aware of the needed capacities and resources that can be provided within the timeframe.

11.) Referral Reporting

Data from the referral process can also be collectively collected, analyzed, and documented into a customized report that underscores trends, statuses, and key actions or supports provided. This is to amplify the responsiveness of the referral mechanism and ensure it contributes to the overall recalibrations of sector or activity-specific and humanitarian programming for responsive actions.

Referral status	Details
Referrals not received	Referral sent to the receiving/responding agency, but it has not confirmed or acknowledged the receipt of referral.
Referrals acknowledged	Receiving/responding agency confirmed receipt of the referral.
Referral accepted	Receiving/responding agency provided feedback that the referral is accepted, and services will be provided (<i>or further referral and investigations are needed</i>).
Referral not accepted	<p>Receiving/Responding agency provided feedback that the referrals are not accepted. Reasons/justifications/details are to be provided by receiving/responding agency in the soonest time possible.</p> <p>Key points to consider why referrals are not accepted or eligible:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If concerned individual or community member does not accept the minimum referral process. ○ Limited or overwhelmed capacity of one or two agencies. ○ If additional critical information is not provided to proceed, and in many cases, contact of an individual or community member for follow-up engagement is lost.

12.) Reporting back to the communities

To secure people’s trust and satisfaction, it is imperative to report back to the communities about:

- Status of cases or issues being reviewed and referred.
- Consultation on the components or details that they do not understand when it comes to accessing the two-way channels, referral processes, and people or agencies managing the case or complaints.

- The reason and the need to change or make adjustments or recalibrations on the available channels and system supporting the referral process.
- The reason and the need to conduct further referral, follow-ups, and investigations.